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**A MECHANISM FOR BALANCED REGIONAL INVESTMENT DEVELOPMENT
 IN RUSSIA IN THE CONTEXT OF STRUCTURAL TRANSFORMATION
 OF THE ECONOMY**

2019-2024

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2024

This article analyzes the dynamics and spatial differentiation of investment activity in the regions of the Russian Federation for the period 2019-2024, identifying key trends and structural shifts in the context of adaptation to new economic realities. Based on a synthesis of data from relevant ministries, rating agencies, and academic research, an original mechanism for state regulation of regional investment processes is proposed. This mechanism is based on the principles of strategic planning, multi-level coordination, and adaptive management with an emphasis on digitalization. A conceptual model for improving the effectiveness of regional investment policy has been developed, integrating tools from the federal, regional, and municipal levels of governance. The scientific novelty of this study lies in its substantiation of a combined top-down and bottom-up approach to distributing responsibilities between institutional levels for managing investment processes in the context of digital transformation. The practical significance of this work lies in the development of specific recommendations for reducing regional disparities and increasing the sustainability of investment development in the constituent entities of the Russian Federation based on 2024 data.

Keywords: regional economy, investment dynamics, spatial differentiation, government regulation, balanced development mechanism, strategic planning, digitalization, investment climate

2019-2024

4,1 %

8,6 %

2024

(21 % 2024)

2019-2024

1. 2022-2024 ., « ».

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2. 2019-2024 .

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• III(2029–2030).
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1. 2022–2024 .

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URL: www.ra-national.ru/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/investicionnaja_privlekatelnost_regionov_2024-3.pdf?ysclid=mhkrjjvoas943884410 (:02.10.2025).

2. // : , .— 2024. — 2(67). — .18-33. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2024-2-18-33. — EDNMYFYXG.

3. // . — URL: minfin.gov.ru/ru/performance/budget/process/utverzhdienie/budget_citizen/?ysclid=mjy6sql8k132415413 (:02.10.2025).

4. // : . — 2024. — 3(68). — .17-33. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2024-3-17-33. — EDNNEOKGD.

5. // . — URL: ach.gov.ru/reports/?ysclid=mjy8eaxxio79158277 (:02.10.2025).

6. // . — 2024. — .10, 1. — .15-22. — DOI 10.18413/2409-1634-2024-10-1-0-2. — EDNOWRTDW.

7. — URL: raexpert.ru/researches/regions/invest_regions_2024/?ysclid=mhkrlyh31e466530522 (02.10.2025).
8. 2036 : 08.05.2025 1161- . — URL: www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_504871/ (: 02.10.2025).
9. , 2024 // . — URL: afkrukon.ru/analitika/post-1708/?ysclid=mhkrn07q2h174654416 (: 02.10.2025).
10. 2024 // . — URL: ach.gov.ru/audit/oper-2024?ysclid=mhkrksgytc399653683 (: 02.10.2025).
11. / // : . — 2025. — 2. — . 67-88. — DOI 10.17323/1999-5431-2025-0-2-67-88. — EDN JLPBXA.
12. // . — URL: www.economy.gov.ru/stat/?ysclid=mjy8dg92mm188645085 (: 02.10.2025).

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

- XII Yezhegodnaya otsenka investitsionnoy regionov Rossii privlekatel'nosti «Razvorot na Vostok». — URL: www.ra-national.ru/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/investicionnaya_privlekatelnost_regionov_2024-3.pdf?ysclid=mhkrjivoas943884410 (data obrashcheniya: 02.10.2025).
- Butova, T. G. Vliyaniye tsifrovyykh tekhnologiy na upravleniye finansovymi aktivami / T. G. Butova, D. D. Burkal'tseva, V. A. Kondrashin // Nauchnyy vestnik: finansy, banki, investitsii. — 2024. — 2(67). — S. 18-33. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2024-2-18-33. — EDN MYFYXG.
- Byudzhet dlya grazhdan // Minfin Rossii. — URL: minfin.gov.ru/ru/performance/budget/process/utverzhdenie/budget_citizen/?ysclid=mjy6sql8kl32415413 (data obrashcheniya: 02.10.2025).
- Voroby va, . I. Gosudarstvennaya finansovaya strategiya Rossiyskoy Federatsii: teoreticheskiye aspekty i praktika realizatsii / . I. Voroby va, O. G. Blazhevich // Nauchnyy vestnik: finansy, banki, investitsii. — 2024. — 3(68). — S. 17-33. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2024-3-17-33. — EDN NEOKGD.
- Godovoy otchet // Schetnaya palata Rossiyskoy Federatsii. — URL: ach.gov.ru/reports/?ysclid=mjy8eaxxi079158277 (data obrashcheniya: 02.10.2025).
- Ibragimova, Z. A. Mekhanizm ustoychivogo razvitiyaregional'nykh ekonomicheskikh sistem / Z. A. Ibragimova // Nauchnyy rezul'tat. Ekonomicheskkiye issledovaniya. — 2024. — T. 10, 1. — S. 15-22. — DOI 10.18413/2409-1634-2024-10-1-0-2. — EDN OWRTDW.
- Investitsionnaya privlekatel'nost' regionov: novyye vyzovy i vozmozhnosti dlya investorov // Ekspert RA. — URL: raexpert.ru/researches/regions/invest_regions_2024/?ysclid=mhkrlyh31e466530522 (data obrashcheniya: 02.10.2025).
- O Kontseptsii ustoychivogo razvitiya korennykh malochislennykh narodov Severa, Sibiri i Dal'nego Vostoka Rossiyskoy Federatsii na period do 2036 goda: Rasporyazheniye Pravitel'stva RF ot 08.05.2025 1161-r. — URL: www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_504871/ (data obrashcheniya: 02.10.2025).
- Obzor itogov makroekonomiki, 2024 goda // RUKON AFK. — URL: afkrukon.ru/analitika/post-1708/?ysclid=mhkrn07q2h174654416 (data obrashcheniya: 02.10.2025).
- Operativnyy doklad za 2024 god // Schetnaya palata Rossiyskoy Federatsii. — URL: ach.gov.ru/audit/oper-2024?ysclid=mhkrksgytc399653683 (data obrashcheniya: 02.10.2025).
- Sanina, A. G. Tsifrovaya transformatsiya i ustoychivoye razvitiye rossiyskikh regionov: otsenki sootnosheniya upravlencheskiye implikatsii / A. G. Sanina, V. A. Khomyakova, A. G. Atayeva // Voprosy gosudarstvennogo i munitsipal'nogo upravleniya. — 2025. — 2. — S. 67-88. — DOI 10.17323/1999-5431-2025-0-2-67-88. — EDN JLPBXA.
- Statistika // Ministerstvo ekonomicheskogo razvitiya Rossiyskoy Federatsii. — URL: www.economy.gov.ru/stat/?ysclid=mjy8dg92mm188645085 (data obrashcheniya: 02.10.2025).

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